

WORK SESSION 'TOWARDS AN ONE HEALTH RISK ANALYSIS SYSTEM FOR ZOOSES IN PORTUGAL'

You are kindly invited for the work session 'Towards an One Health Risk Analysis System for Zoonoses in Portugal'.

The session will be held at INIAV, Quinta do Marquês, Oeiras on the 22nd (9:30 to 17:00) and 23rd (9:00 to 13:00) of November 2021. Spoken languages will be Portuguese and English.

WHY THIS WORK SESSION?

In Europe there are already legislation and, for many (especially the foodborne one) zoonoses, surveillance systems that allow for early detection, timely response and control. However, new and emerging zoonoses, which are beyond the scope of the current surveillance systems, many having wild or domestic animals as reservoirs like the current Covid-19 pandemic, can become public and/or animal health threats. These threats can occur in any country and their signalling, risk assessment, response and control requires collaboration between the sectors of animal health, human health and environment. In The Netherlands and the UK, such **One Health Risk Analysis Systems** for (emerging) zoonoses have been implemented, with governmental support, only after going through a major outbreak respectively Q fever and BSE. Such preparedness is crucial and should preferably be organised in peacetime.

It is important to know how our country is organized to respond to similar situations with the involvement and collaboration of the different sectors (One Health).

An One Health approach is also encouraged by the Global Health Security Agenda, which aims the introduction of **operational national systems to support multi-sectoral reporting in situations of suspected outbreaks of zoonotic origin**, in the early stage of emergency (before transmission efficient from person to person). These systems aim to analyze outbreaks that occur in animals and humans at a similar time and/or location. However, due to different organization of food production systems and ministries, geographical factors and cultural differences between countries, there is no blueprint for such **One Health Risk Analysis Systems**.

In this work session we will analyze how the network for signalling and response to zoonoses is organized in Portugal and identify its various actors.

WHY USE SYSTEMS THINKING?

Systems thinking is a way of looking at and talking about reality that helps us understand and work with complex systems that interact with their environment. It helps conceptualizing many elements that interact and behave, and that are in their totality at times beyond our capacity to grasp. Systems thinking allows us to analyse details without losing the sense for the whole. It offers a set of tools for capturing, analysing and communicating about systems.

Watch a 2-minute introduction by the systems thinking pioneer Peter Senge at MIT:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eXdzKBWDraM>

Watch a 5-minute video about systems thinking in public health:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GPW0j2Bo_eY

WHAT WILL WE DO?

Using a **systems thinking approach** to reach a better understanding of the interactions between the Portuguese actors of zoonoses, we will:

- Identify the actors involved in the signalling and response to zoonoses in Portugal;
- Discuss their roles, motives, and perspectives;
- Gain an inventory of existing links and relationships;
- Possibly, include biological and/or social mechanisms related to zoonoses.

The session will result in a visual representation, or “map”, of the way the field of zoonoses signalling and response is organized in Portugal today.

With the **map**, we will:

- Identify critical control points for the evaluation of the signalling and control of zoonoses;
- Identify missing communication links;
- Identify missing data and knowledge;
- Gain a better understanding of the dynamics between different elements, sectors and disciplines;
- Gain a holistic view on biological and social dynamics involved in zoonoses;
- Identify next steps in improving One Health risk analysis of zoonoses in Portugal.

WHY SHOULD YOU ATTEND TO THIS SESSION?

To gain a common vision on how to tackle zoonotic diseases in Portugal with a One Health approach

- Get insight in how signalling and response to zoonoses is organised and who plays a role;
- Get insight in where collaboration between different sectors involved in zoonoses can be improved;
- Get a peek into what systems thinking is and how it can help tackling wicked (= complex) problems;
- Experience systems mapping as a way to draft the context, useful for many situations.

A SESSION UNDER THE PROJECT “COHESIVE: ONE HEALTH STRUCTURE IN EUROPE”

The COHESIVE project, which is part of the One Health EJP consortium in which more than 38 European partners are involved, is led by Dr. Kitty Maassen from the Dutch National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). One of the aims of the project is to support

member states in Europe in creating One Health approaches to strengthen the collaboration between food, medical, and veterinary professionals with respect to early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses threats, through the development of procedures and tools that enhance the ability to identify, share and communicate zoonotic warning signs, as well as carry out the risk assessment and management of outbreaks in a One Health system. In this context, a website is being created, containing implementation guidelines to support countries organizing One Health risk analysis activities. For this, it is important to determine the exact objective and the context in which the risk analysis will be organized, so the mapping of existing systems in the country is fundamental.

A WORKSHOP FACILITATED BY SIMON RÜEGG

Dr. Simon Rüegg is a veterinary epidemiologist and experienced systems thinker at the University of Zürich, Switzerland. He has within the EU COST Action “Network for Evaluation of One Health” edited the “Integrated approaches to health: a handbook for the evaluation of One Health”. Further, he has published many peer-reviewed articles on the subject, and has been solicited for presentations and workshops by the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the American Veterinary Medical Association, the US Defence Threat Reduction Agency and the French CIRAD, among others. For more details, please consult Dr Rüegg’s [researcher ID profile](#).